

**Alternative Dispute Resolution in Tanzania's Oil and Gas Sector:
An Outline of the Role of the Energy and Water Utilities Regulatory Authority**

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Abstract:

This article examines the position and role of the Energy and Water Utilities Regulatory Authority (EWURA) in the settlement of disputes in the Tanzanian energy sector, through the use of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) mechanisms. To do this, the study explores the regulatory framework of the Energy and Water Utilities Regulatory Authority. It assesses the adequacy of the existing legal provisions, institutional practices, and procedural frameworks governing dispute resolution between investors, operators, and the state. Although mediation was incorporated into the regulatory framework to promote efficiency, transparency, and investor confidence, some challenges continue to hinder its potentials. The article concludes by recommending legal and institutional reforms to strengthen Alternative Dispute Resolution mechanisms for sustainable dispute resolution in Tanzania's oil and gas sector.

Keywords: Energy, Complaints, Mediation, Alternative Dispute Resolution, Enforcement. Tanzania.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Tanzania's oil and gas sector has emerged as one of the most significant pillars of its economic transformation strategy, particularly following the discovery of substantial natural gas reserves in the southern regions such as Mtwara and Lindi¹. The development of this sector promises to enhance energy security, stimulate foreign investment, and generate substantial government revenue. Tanzania has been exploring for oil and gas for more than half a century. The first natural gas discovery was made on the Songo Songo Island in 1974 followed by another one in the Mnazi Bay in 1982. In 2004 and 2006 commercial production of natural gas on the Songo Songo Island and in the Mnazi Bay commenced, respectively. From 2010 Tanzania has witnessed further exploration and discoveries of significant quantities of natural gas both on- and off-shore². However, the complexity of oil and gas operations, which often involve multinational corporations, local contractors, and community participants, inevitably gives rise to various commercial, environmental, and regulatory disputes³.

To manage these disputes effectively, Tanzania has sought to establish strong legal and institutional frameworks that promote transparency, predictability, and investor confidence. The Energy and Water Utilities Regulatory Authority, established under⁴ plays a central role in regulating the energy, petroleum, and water sectors. The authority's mandate includes licensing, tariff regulation, consumer protection, and dispute resolution among the members within the energy and petroleum industries.

2. THE ROLE OF EWURA

The Energy and Water Utilities Regulatory Authority functions as a quasi-judicial regulatory body responsible for ensuring fair play and compliance within Tanzania's liberalized energy market. Under section 6(1)⁵, the Authority is mandated to facilitate the resolution of complaints and disputes between licensees and consumers. In the oil and gas sector, this extends to disputes arising from contractual relationships, regulatory compliance, or service delivery issues. To discharge this mandate, the regulatory authority established the Energy and Water Utilities Regulatory Authority (Consumer Complaints Settlement Procedure) Rules, 2012 which provided a framework for handling complaints through Alternative Dispute Resolution mechanisms such as mediation, negotiation, and conciliation before resorting to formal adjudication. These rules have gone through several amendments. In Article 13, the Energy and Water Utilities

¹Barongo, S. (2023). Oil and gas in Tanzania: How it all started. Dar es Salaam: Mkuki na Nyota Publishers
²Ministry of Energy and Minerals. (2013). The National Natural Gas Policy of Tanzania. Dar es Salaam: Government of Tanzania, <https://tzdpg.or.tz/storage/2022/09/National-Gas-Policy-.pdf> (Accessed on 1st October 2024).

³Lee, B., & Dupuy, K. (2016). *Petro-governance in Tanzania: Opportunities and challenges*. Bergen, Norway: Chr. Michelsen Institute.

⁴The Energy and Water Utilities Regulatory Authority Act [Cap 414 R.E. 2023]

⁵Ibid, Section 6

Regulatory Authority (Consumer Complaints Settlement Procedure) Rules, 2012 provided as follows:

- 13-(1) The Unit shall, as part of investigation, attempt to resolve the complaint in an amicable manner within sixty days from the date of filing the complaint.
- (2) During mediation in sub-rule (1) an officer of the Authority or any other person to be agreed by the parties, may act as a mediator.
- (3) An amicable settlement reached shall be reduced into writing in a form prescribed in the Fifth Schedule and shall be signed by the parties who shall furnish a copy thereof to the Authority for registration.
- (4) The settlement reached under sub-rule (3) shall, upon registration by the Authority, be deemed to be the award of the Authority.

This framework aligns with Tanzania's broader policy shift toward non-adversarial methods of resolving disputes, as reflected in the Arbitration Act No. 2 of 2020, which recognizes Alternative Dispute Resolution as an efficient and complementary method of achieving justice outside traditional court processes.

3. MAJOR LEGAL PROVISIONS INCORPORATING EWURA INTO OIL AND GAS DISPUTE RESOLUTION

In the Petroleum Act, issues of dispute resolution are covered by Section 247⁶, which stipulates that parties should initially seek amicable settlement through negotiation or other mutually agreed upon methods. Where amicable resolution fails, disputes may be referred to arbitration or other Alternative Dispute Resolution mechanisms, as provided in contractual agreements.

Section 247 of the Petroleum Act states that:

- (1) Any dispute between a licensee and a customer or between licensees relating to application of this Act may be filed with EWURA for adjudication.
- (2) Nothing in this section shall be construed to prevent a licensee, a customer or the Government, in its capacity as a party to any agreement relating to gas industry, from agreeing to resolve any dispute arising out of any agreement between them or any third

⁶Section 246 The Petroleum Act [CAP. 392 R.E. 2023].

parties, through binding arbitration or adjudicated in ordinary courts of law. 151 No.21 The Petroleum Act 2015 (3) A person who is aggrieved by any decision of EWURA under this section may, within fourteen days from the date of the decision, appeal to the Fair Competition Tribunal for determination.

The Oil and Gas Revenues Management Act, under Section 6⁷ establishes a clear framework for the collection and auditing of oil and gas revenues, assigning the Tanzania Revenue Authority and the National Oil Company as the principal collectors of all government oil and gas revenues. Specifically, it differentiates between tax-based revenues, to be managed by the Tanzania Revenue Authority, and non-tax revenues, such as surface rentals, signature bonuses, and training fees, which are to be collected and retained by the National Oil Company for subsector development purposes.

However, given the interactions between more than two institutions involved in collection and management, possible disputes may arise concerning revenue assessment, accountability, and institutional authority, particularly where overlapping mandates exist between the Tanzania Revenue Authority, the National Oil Company, and the Ministry of Energy. The provision under subsection (4) of the same law, empowers the Minister to appoint another government entity to assume revenue collection responsibilities in cases of insolvency, policy change, or share flotation by the National Oil Company⁸. This administrative flexibility, while essential, may also generate conflicts of competence or interpretation among government bodies or contractors.

The Energy and Water Utilities Regulatory Authority Act, under, Section 34⁹ empowers the authority to handle disputes between service providers and consumers or between regulated entities themselves. The Act encourages parties to first attempt an amicable settlement¹⁰. Where this is not achievable, the authority may facilitate mediation or refer the matter to arbitration. This structured approach ensures that disputes are resolved fairly, quickly, and cost-effectively, safeguarding the interests of smaller stakeholders while maintaining regulatory oversight. However, the Act cannot operate in isolation without the presence of its rules. Thus, under Section 40 of the same law, it decides to come up with rules that give a clear procedure for handling the situations that arise under the oil and gas.

⁷Section 6 of The Oil and Gas Revenues Management Act [Cap. 328 R.E. 2023]

⁸Ibid,

⁹The Energy and Water Utilities Regulatory Authority Act, [CAP. 414 R.E. 2023]

¹⁰Ibid. Section 34

4. PROCEDURES FOR SETTLEMENT OF DISPUTES UNDER THE ENERGY AND WATER UTILITIES REGULATORY AUTHORITY (CONSUMER COMPLAINTS SETTLEMENT PROCEDURE) RULES, 2020

The Energy and Water Utilities Regulatory Authority (Consumer Complaints Settlement Procedure) Rules, 2020 provide a detailed legal framework for the resolution of consumer disputes within the energy, water, and petroleum sectors. These Rules emphasize Alternative Dispute Resolution, particularly mediation, as the first mechanism to ensure efficiency, fairness, and cost-effectiveness before engaging in formal adjudicative proceedings. The procedures can be summarized as follows:

a. Lodging of complaints

A consumer, consumer group, or authorized representative may file a written complaint to the Energy and Water Utilities Regulatory Authority. The complaint must disclose reasonable grounds for investigation¹¹. Upon receipt, the regulator assesses the complaint to determine whether it is properly filed, within its jurisdiction, and not frivolous or already pending before another competent forum such as a court, tribunal, or arbitral body. If found inadmissible, the complaint is rejected. Once the regulatory authority accepts a complaint, it officially registers it for investigation. The Authority notifies the respondent and may request further documentation or clarification to ascertain the issues in dispute. This stage ensures procedural fairness and transparency in the handling of complaints.

b. Investigation and mediation

After acceptance, the authority initiates an investigation into the complaint and simultaneously undertakes a mediation process aimed at achieving an amicable settlement within sixty (60) days¹². A mediator appointed by the regulatory authority facilitates negotiations between the parties to resolve the matter collaboratively. If the parties reach a settlement, the terms are reduced into writing and submitted to the Authority for adoption. Once approved, the settlement becomes an enforceable award of the regulatory, carrying the same effect as a binding decision.

c. Referral to the division for formal hearing and decision enforcement

If mediation fails to yield a resolution, the complaint is referred to regulatory Division, which acts as a quasi-judicial body¹³. The Division conducts a formal hearing involving the examination of witnesses, presentation of evidence, and application of relevant laws. This stage represents the adjudicative phase of dispute settlement within the Authority's

¹¹ Rule 4 of The Energy and Water Utilities Regulatory Authority (Consumer Complaints Settlement Procedure) Rules, 2020.

¹² Ibid, Rule 13 & 14

¹³ Ibid, Rule 17

administrative structure. The Division's determination constitutes the final decision of the authority. The decision is binding upon the parties and may be enforced through the High Court of Tanzania. This gives the Authority's rulings legal force equivalent to that of judicial decisions.

Although the Rules successfully promote mediation as the primary Alternative Dispute Resolution mechanism, they do not provide for arbitration as a subsequent stage if mediation fails. Instead, disputes are directed to the internal Division for adjudication. This limitation restricts the full application of Alternative Dispute Resolution principles, as arbitration, being an independent and binding process, could enhance neutrality, confidentiality, and finality in resolving complex disputes on oil and gas that often involve high commercial stakes and technical intricacies.

5. CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS AFFECTING ALTERNATIVE DISPUTE RESOLUTION UNDER EWURA

This section examines the major challenges and limitations affecting the implementation and effectiveness of Alternative Dispute Resolution under the Energy and Water Utilities Regulatory Authority framework.

a. Absence of mandatory provisions of the law

Mediation is fundamentally a voluntary dispute resolution process, relying on the consent and cooperation of parties to achieve an amicable settlement. Its core principle is party autonomy, allowing disputing parties to control the outcome without recourse to formal litigation. While the authority recognizes Alternative Dispute Resolution and has established mediation procedures for oil and gas disputes, the current framework does not make arbitration a mandatory next step if mediation fails. Arbitration is only mentioned as an optional mechanism, leaving parties without a clear procedural escalation.

b. Cultural beliefs

A significant practical challenge affecting the implementation and effectiveness of Alternative Dispute Resolution under authority's framework is the deeply ingrained cultural preference for litigation. Many respondents perceived court rulings as more legitimate, authoritative, and final than outcomes achieved through Alternative Dispute Resolution mechanisms such as mediation or arbitration. This belief influences the choices of businesses and legal practitioners, often making litigation the default route for resolving disputes in the oil and gas sector.

c. Enforcement issues

A major limitation affecting the effectiveness of Alternative Dispute Resolution under authority is the challenge of enforcing mediation agreements and arbitral awards. While Alternative Dispute Resolution is intended to provide a faster and more efficient resolution compared to formal litigation, the current enforcement process often requires parties to make formal applications to the High Court. This step can be slow, costly, and hindered by procedural technicalities, which ultimately reduce the practical benefits of Alternative Dispute Resolution.

d. Incorporation of arbitration in procedural sequence

The procedural framework under the Energy and Water Utilities Regulatory Authority (Consumer Complaints Settlement Procedure) Rules, 2020¹⁴, primarily relies on mediation as the first and often only step in resolving oil and gas disputes. While mediation is intended to provide an amicable and cost-effective resolution, the absence of a mandatory subsequent arbitration process creates a significant gap in the dispute resolution pathway. This procedural limitation often leaves unresolved disputes in a state of uncertainty, potentially escalating to formal courts and resulting in delays and increased costs for parties involved.

e. Establishment of alternative dispute resolution division

The current regulatory framework¹⁵ does not include a dedicated unit to manage Alternative Dispute Resolution processes. Alternative Dispute Resolution activities, including mediation and any arbitration proceedings, are currently handled within general administrative units of the authority¹⁶. This arrangement limits institutional specialization and often results in inconsistent handling of disputes, particularly those that involve the technical complexities of the oil and gas sector. The absence of a specialized Alternative Dispute Resolution division may also reduce stakeholder confidence, as parties may perceive the dispute resolution process as lacking expertise and focus.

6. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that Tanzania has a foundational legal framework supporting Alternative Dispute Resolution, including provisions for mediation under the Energy and Water Utilities Regulatory Authority (Consumer Complaints Settlement Procedure) Rules, 2020. However, the main challenges, such as the absence of a mandatory procedural sequence, enforcement difficulties, low awareness among stakeholders,

¹⁴The Energy and Water Utilities Regulatory Authority (Consumer Complaints Settlement Procedure) Rules, 2020

¹⁵The Energy and Water Utilities Regulatory Authority [CAP 414 R.E 2023]

¹⁶Ibid, Section 7(1)(d).

cultural preferences for litigation, and limited institutional support, significantly reduce the effectiveness of Alternative Dispute Resolution in practice.

Therefore, while the regulatory framework provides a basis for dispute resolution, it falls short in ensuring participatory, timely, and equitable outcomes. To address these gaps, the study recommends legal and institutional reforms, including the institutionalization of Alternative Dispute Resolution mechanisms within regulations, the inclusion of structured mediation followed by mandatory arbitration, the creation of specialized Alternative Dispute Resolution units, and measures to enhance procedural justice, transparency, and stakeholder confidence in resolving oil and gas disputes. Implementing these reforms is crucial for establishing Alternative Dispute Resolution as a reliable, efficient, and trusted mechanism within Tanzania's oil and gas sector.